

Original article

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CHOOSING THE RIGHT VERTIPORT LAYOUT: CAPACITY AND COST COMPARISON

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Abstract: *Vertiports, as ground infrastructure, represent one of the key enablers of the Urban Air Mobility (UAM) concept implementation. Even though vertiport location and vertiport capacity are identified as two aspects that can substantially impact UAM service performance, there is a notable lack of comprehensive studies in this field. In this paper, we estimate the capacity and area of the different vertiport layouts relying on published vertiport design criteria and operational concepts assumed based on relevant literature. We calculate the vertiport infrastructure cost by considering the area, the number of electric chargers, and whether the vertiport is located at ground level or on a rooftop. Our analysis includes multi-function, linear, pier, and satellite layouts, featuring one or two Final Approach and Take-Off areas (FATOs) and two to ten gates. By examining the trade-off between infrastructure cost and capacity, we offer insights to guide future decision-makers in selecting appropriate vertiport layouts based on available space and location.*

Keywords: *Urban Air Mobility, vertiport, layout, capacity, infrastructure cost, informed decision-making.*

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